

Questionnaire n°3 (Farm consultants)

Dear participant,

This survey will help us know your views on Decision Support Systems designed to guide farmers towards a better pesticide management. To proceed with the survey please read carefully the following sentences and tick the relevant boxes as appropriate.

- I confirm that I have read and understood the terms and conditions for participating in the study.
- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and with no foreseeable consequences.
- I agree to take part in this study.
- I agree that the data gathered in this study may be stored (after being anonymized) in a secure storage facility and will be destroyed five years after the study ends.

1. In which country are you based?

2. Which is your age group?

- 18 to 25
- 25 to 34
- 36 to 49
- 49 to 60
- 60 or more

3. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female

4. What is the highest degree you have attained?

Vocational qualification

Bachelor's degree

Master's degree

PhD

Others (please specify)

5. How long have you been working in farm consulting?

Less than 2 years

Between 2 and 5 years

Between 5 and 10 years

More than 10 years

6. What type of crop(s) are you specialized in?

Primary:

Other:

7. When a farmer calls you for the first time, would you expect them to have found you by chance or were you recommended by someone else?

By chance

Recommended

8. When farmers call you for the first time, how often did they first use a decision support system?

Less than 20% of cases

From 20 to 50% of cases

From 50 to 80% of cases

More than 80% of cases

9. Objectively, to what extent do you think decision support systems in general are adapted to farmers? Rate it on a scale from 1 (worse) to 7 (best).

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2

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10. Have you already received feedback from farmers on decision support systems?

Yes

No

11. If yes, is that feedback globally positive?

Yes

No

12. Some farmers choose not to use decision support systems. What is the main reason in your opinion?

Lack of trust

Habits

Uncomfortable with new technologies

Price (too expensive)

Other reasons (please specify)

13. Do you think that most of decision support systems take into account a large enough set of parameters to be accurate in their diagnostic? If no, what additional parameters could also be taken into account?

Yes

No

14. How often do you use decision support systems to find the best pest management strategy in a given situation?

Very often

Often

Sometimes

Rarely

Never

15. Do you recommend your clients to use decision support systems?

Yes

No

16. Do you think decision support systems are a substitute or complement to your job?

Substitute

Complement

17. Does the use of a decision support system improve your decision making process and productivity?

No use of DSL at all

No improvement

Non-negligible improvement

Big improvement

18. Is simplified graphical output from a decision support system enough for your needs?

Yes

No, both graphic and textual outputs are needed

19. Do you require evidence based proofs from developers?

- No
- If available always

20. Do you help farmers to buy a decision support system?

- No
- Help with grants
- Negotiate with developers for price

21. How hard is to move away from the current tools to the new developed once?

- Hard
- It takes some time
- Not hard at all

22. Do you use the same decision support system as your clients?

- I use the same **decision support system**
- I use more generalized version of their **decision support system**
- No, I use different **decision support systems**

23. Do you consider that the age of your client influences the use of decision support systems?

- No
- Age barriers are manageable
- older generations think that using a **decision support system** is not for them

24. What is the farm scale structure of the majority of your clients?

- Small family farms
- Midsize farms
- Large farms
- Mixed

25. What is the prevailing crop type of your clients?

Primary: _____

Other:

26. Do you provide access to IT education to your clients?

- No
- Upon their request
- Yes, regardless of their requirements

27. Do you have access to speed internet?

- No
- In the office but not in all the fields of my clients
- Yes, both in the office and in the fields of my clients

28. Do you need to satisfy some legislative or market requirements (e.g. limits of fertilizers use, time of pesticide applications, ...) ?

- No
- Some general requirements
- Yes, I have to collect detailed evidences of my clients

29. Do you have access to marketing information about decision support systems?

- No
- Occasionally only
- Yes, I'm subscribed to receive news concerning decision support systems

30. Have you followed a manufacturer's demonstration of a decision support system?

- Never
- Occasionally by invitation
- Regularly

31. In general terms, how would you imagine a platform integrating and giving access to several decision support systems? Comment next to each item below how important you consider it or leave the space blank otherwise.

Interface simplicity

Access to multiple DSS

Information to select DSS

The same user interface for all DSS

Risk alerts on one screen for multiple pests and multiple crops

Automatic alerts (via text or email)

Pest observations collected from users and providers

